

**AZƏRBAYCAN RESPUBLİKASI ELM VƏ TƏHSİL NAZİRLİYİ
SUMQAYIT DÖVLƏT UNİVERSİTETİ**

**TÜRKİYE CUMHURİYETİ YÜKSEK ÖĞRETİM KURULU
MALATYA TURGUT ÖZAL ÜNİVERSİTESİ**

**КЫРГЫЗ РЕСПУБЛИКАСЫНЫН БИЛИМ БЕРҮҮ ЖАНА ИЛИМ МИНИСТРЛИГИ
ОШ МАМЛЕКЕТТИК УНИВЕРСИТЕТИ**

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*I Uluslararası bilimsel konferans
(22-23 mayıs 2025)*

**ТҮРК ТИЛДҮҮ МАМЛЕКЕТТЕРДИН ЭКОНОМИКАЛЫК РЕСУРСТАРЫН
ЭФФЕКТИВДҮҮ ПАЙДАЛАНУУНУН АКТУАЛДУУ МАСЕЛЕЛЕРИ**

*I Эл аралык илимий конференция
(22-23-май, 2025-жыл)*

**АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ
ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ РЕСУРСОВ ТЮРКОЯЗЫЧНЫХ ГОСУДАРСТВ**

*I Международная научная конференция
(22-23 мая 2025 года)*

**ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF EFFICIENT USE OF ECONOMIC RESOURCES OF TURKIC-
SPEAKING STATES**

*I International scientific conference
(22-23 May, 2025)*

SUMQAYIT - 2025

Резюме

Танрыверди П.А.

Модернизация транспортно-логистической инфраструктуры государств-членов Союза Тюркских Государств и реализация транзитного потенциала

В статье рассматривается значение реализации конкурентных преимуществ и транзитного потенциала международного транспортного коридора «Зангезур», внедрения цифровых таможенных систем, в целях углубления экономических отношений между государствами-членами в рамках Тюркского союза, упрощения торговли и транзита, определены направления модернизации и совершенствования таможенной, транспортной и логистической инфраструктуры, а также на основе оценки транзитных возможностей Азербайджана которые могут способствовать развитию международных транспортных коридоров перечислены меры и реформы, которые необходимо осуществить в этих сферах.

Ключевые слова: Союз Тюркских Государств, международный транспортный коридор, транспортная инфраструктура, логистическая инфраструктура, внешняя торговля, грузопотоки, транзитный коридор

Summary

Tanriverdi P.A.

Modernization of Transport and Logistics Infrastructure of Member States of the Union of Turkic States and Realization of Transit Potential

The article discusses the importance of realizing the competitive advantages and transit potential of the Zangezur international transport corridor, introducing digital customs systems, in order to deepen economic relations between member states within the Turkic Union, simplifying trade and transit, identifying areas for modernization and improvement of customs, transport and logistics infrastructure, and listing measures and reforms that need to be implemented in these areas based on an assessment of Azerbaijan's transit capabilities that can contribute to the development of international transport corridors.

Key words: Union of Turkic States, international transport corridor, transport infrastructure, logistics infrastructure, foreign trade, cargo flows, transit corridor

RENEWABLE ENERGY ADVANCEMENT IN AZERBAIJAN AND EUROPE: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

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Summary: *This paper compares renewable energy development in Azerbaijan and Europe, focusing on opportunities, challenges, and efforts in both regions. Azerbaijan, traditionally reliant on fossil fuels, is diversifying its energy mix through solar, wind, and green hydrogen projects. Europe leads globally in renewable energy, driven by EU climate policies and technological advancements. Both regions have made progress but face challenges like infrastructure, regulatory reforms, and international cooperation. The paper examines these themes through case studies, data, and policy frameworks.*

Key words: *Renewable Energy, Solar Energy, Wind Power, Green Hydrogen, Energy Transition, Energy Security, Sustainable Development*

1. Introduction

Azerbaijan, while traditionally known for its abundant oil and gas reserves, has gradually recognized the importance of renewable energy as part of its long-term strategy for energy diversification and climate change mitigation. With the global energy transition gaining momentum, Azerbaijan aims to increase the share of renewable energy in its energy mix to 30% by 2030. The country has considerable potential in wind, solar, and hydropower, which, if harnessed effectively, could substantially contribute to its energy security and environmental sustainability. Similarly, Europe has been a leader in renewable energy adoption, with several countries implementing robust policies and achieving notable advancements in solar, wind, and biomass energy.

This paper seeks to provide a comparative analysis of renewable energy developments in Azerbaijan and Europe, examining their respective progress, opportunities, challenges, and policy frameworks. Through this analysis, the study highlights both the achievements and common obstacles encountered by both regions in their pursuit of a sustainable energy future.

2. Literature Review

The concept of the green economy, introduced by the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) in 2011, has emerged as a vital strategy for sustainable development, aiming to balance economic growth with environmental preservation. It focuses on reducing environmental impacts while fostering inclusive economic development. The green economy addresses global challenges like climate change, resource depletion, and biodiversity loss (UNEP, 2011). Its core principles emphasize low-carbon development, resource efficiency, and social inclusivity, ultimately aiming to decouple economic growth from environmental degradation.

At its core, the green economy advocates a shift from traditional models based on fossil fuels to sustainable, renewable energy sources. UNEP (2011) stresses the importance of policies supporting low-carbon development, energy efficiency, and a circular economy. Unlike conventional growth models, which link economic progress to resource consumption, the green economy promotes "decoupling" growth from environmental harm (Hertin et al., 2008) [2]. By integrating environmental considerations into economic decision-making, the green economy supports ecosystem protection and sustainable production practices (World Bank, 2019).

Transitioning to a green economy offers substantial economic benefits. Investments in clean technologies, renewable energy, and green infrastructure stimulate growth and create jobs (OECD, 2020). The International Labour Organization (ILO, 2020) highlights the potential for job creation in sectors such as renewable energy, environmental consulting, and sustainable agriculture [4]. For instance, the renewable energy sector has rapidly expanded, generating millions of jobs in solar and wind industries (IRENA, 2020) [5]. Moreover, green technologies reduce dependence on imported fossil fuels, thereby enhancing energy security and lowering long-term energy costs (IEA, 2021).

Investments in green technologies also improve resource efficiency, leading to cost savings and enhanced competitiveness. Promoting energy efficiency and better resource management can lower operational costs and stabilize national economies by reducing vulnerability to global commodity price fluctuations (OECD, 2020) [8]. Additionally, the green economy opens new markets for eco-friendly products, driving innovation and fostering sustainable growth (European Commission, 2022).

Countries embracing green economy principles have made notable strides in mitigating climate change. The International Energy Agency (IEA, 2021) [3] reports that renewable energy transitions contribute significantly to reducing carbon emissions and achieving global climate targets. The European Union's expansion of renewable energy capacity has notably reduced carbon emissions (European Commission, 2022) [1]. Green policies and clean technologies are also vital to achieving the Paris Agreement's climate goals, such as limiting global temperature rise and achieving carbon neutrality (UNDP, 2021) [10].

Azerbaijan's renewable energy potential, particularly in solar, wind, and hydropower, has attracted significant attention in recent research. The Caspian Sea offers substantial offshore wind energy potential, while Azerbaijan's location is ideal for solar energy generation. However, challenges such as insufficient infrastructure, a lack of foreign investment, and an incomplete policy framework hinder renewable energy development.

3. Methodology

This study employs a comparative research methodology, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative analyses. Data related to renewable energy capacities and projects in Azerbaijan and Europe were collected from official sources, including the Ministry of Energy of Azerbaijan, the International Energy Agency (IEA), and the European Commission. The quantitative analysis focuses on assessing the renewable energy capacity in both regions, while the qualitative aspect examines policy frameworks, technological advancements, and challenges faced by each region. Additionally, case studies of key renewable energy projects in Azerbaijan and Europe are presented to illustrate successful models and common obstacles in implementation.

4. Results and Discussion

Azerbaijan has made notable progress in expanding its renewable energy capacity. As of 2023, the total installed capacity from renewable energy sources in the country stands at 1,687.8 MW, representing 20.3% of the total installed electricity generation capacity. The breakdown of renewable energy sources shown in table 1.

Table 1. Renewable energy sources in Azerbaijan

Energy Source	Capacity (MW)	Percentage of Total
Hydropower	1,301.8	15.6%
Wind Power	66.4	0.8%
Solar Power	281.9	3.4%
Bioenergy	37.7	0.5%
Total	1,687.8	20.3%

Source: The Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Azerbaijan[8].

Key projects in Azerbaijan include:

- ✓ The Garadagh Solar Power Plant (230 MW), which is the largest solar facility in the Caspian region.
- ✓ The Khizi-Absheron Wind Power Plant (240 MW), a major project aimed at tapping into Azerbaijan's wind energy potential [6].
- ✓ Ongoing developments in offshore wind energy in the Caspian Sea, with an estimated potential capacity of up to 157 GW.

Azerbaijan has also expressed interest in establishing a Green Energy Zone in its liberated territories, further emphasizing its commitment to renewable energy development. The country is additionally exploring the potential for green hydrogen production as part of its energy diversification strategy.

Renewable Energy Capacity in Europe (2023)

Europe has made substantial progress in the renewable energy sector, driven largely by the EU's ambitious climate and energy policies. As of 2023, Europe's total renewable energy capacity has reached approximately 1,000 GW, with wind and solar power representing the largest shares (see Table 2).

Table 2. Renewable energy sources in Europe

ENERGY SOURCE	CAPACITY (GW)	PERCENTAGE OF TOTAL
WIND POWER	240	24%
SOLAR POWER	350	35%
HYDROPOWER	250	25%
BIOMASS	50	5%
TOTAL	1,000	100%

Source: Eurostat (2023)

Countries such as Germany, Spain, and Denmark have been leaders in both onshore and offshore wind energy, with the United Kingdom, Netherlands, and Denmark at the forefront of offshore wind energy development. The EU has also committed to scaling up green hydrogen production, aiming to decarbonize industries and enhance energy security.

Source: Eurostat ([nrg_ind_ren](#))

Figure 1. The share of renewable energy in gross final energy consumption(%) in 2023.

In 2023, the European Union (EU) achieved a 24.5% share of renewable energy in its gross final energy consumption. This represents an increase of approximately 1.5 percentage points compared to 2022 and nearly triples the share recorded in 2004, which was 9.6%. The EU Directive 2023/2413, aimed at promoting the use of renewable energy sources, has raised the EU's renewable energy target for 2030 from 32% to 42.5%, with a further goal of reaching 45%. As a result, EU member states are required to significantly accelerate their efforts to meet the updated target for 2030, necessitating an almost 20-percentage point increase in the share of renewable energy sources in the gross final energy consumption of EU (see Figure 1) [9].

Common Challenges and Opportunities

Both Azerbaijan and Europe face several common challenges in renewable energy development, including:

- ✓ **Grid Integration:** Integrating variable renewable energy sources into existing power grids presents significant technical and infrastructural challenges, particularly with regard to energy storage and balancing supply and demand.
- ✓ **Regulatory and Policy Frameworks:** Both regions require further development of regulatory frameworks that support renewable energy investments and facilitate the transition to a low-carbon energy system.
- ✓ **Technological Innovation:** Advances in renewable energy technologies, including energy storage, offshore wind, and green hydrogen, are crucial to overcoming the challenges posed by intermittency and ensuring reliable energy supply.

Despite these challenges, both regions also present significant opportunities for growth, particularly in offshore wind energy and green hydrogen. There is potential for enhanced international cooperation, particularly in areas such as cross-border electricity trading, joint research initiatives, and sharing best practices in renewable energy deployment.

5. Conclusion

The green economy represents a transformative approach to sustainable development, integrating economic growth with environmental conservation and social equity. By prioritizing renewable energy, resource efficiency, and low-carbon technologies, it offers a viable solution to global challenges such as climate change, resource depletion, and pollution.

Azerbaijan and Europe have made significant strides in renewable energy development, each reflecting their unique challenges, opportunities, and policy landscapes. Azerbaijan, although still in the early stages of its renewable energy transition, has considerable potential in wind, solar, and hydropower, with ambitious plans to increase the share of renewables in its energy mix by 2030. Europe, on the other hand, is

already a global leader in renewable energy, with advanced infrastructure and policies supporting further growth. Both regions face common obstacles, such as grid integration and the need for regulatory reforms, but also share opportunities for collaboration, particularly in offshore wind energy and green hydrogen development. By leveraging their respective strengths and working together, Azerbaijan and Europe can accelerate their transitions to sustainable energy systems, contributing to global efforts to combat climate change.

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Xülasə

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Azərbaycanda və Avropada bərpa olunan enerjinin inkişafı: problemlər və imkanlar

Bu məqalə Azərbaycan və Avropada bərpa olunan enerji inkişafını müqayisə edir, hər iki regiondakı imkanlar, çətinliklər və səylər üzərində fokuslanır. Neft və qazdan asılı olan Azərbaycan, enerji sahəsini günəş, külək və yaşıl hidrogen layihələri ilə diversifikasiya edir. Avropa isə, AI-nin iqlim siyasətləri və texnoloji inkişafdan irəli gələrək bərpa olunan enerji sahəsində liderlik edir. Hər iki region infrastruktur, tənzimləmə islahatları və beynəlxalq əməkdaşlıq kimi problemlərlə üzləşir. Bu məsələlər nümunələr, məlumatlar və siyasət çərçivələri ilə təhlil olunur.

Açar sözlər: *Bərpa olunan enerji, Günəş enerjisi, Külək enerjisi, Yaşıl hidrogen, Enerji keçidi, Enerji təhlükəsizliyi, Davamlı inkişaf*

Резюме

Аббасов Н.Р.

Развитие возобновляемых источников энергии в Азербайджане и Европе: проблемы и возможности

Статья сравнивает развитие возобновляемых источников энергии в Азербайджане и Европе, с акцентом на возможности, проблемы и усилия в обеих регионах. Азербайджан, традиционно зависимый от ископаемых видов топлива, диверсифицирует энергобаланс через солнечные, ветряные

и «зеленые» водородные проекты. Европа лидирует в возобновляемой энергетике благодаря политике ЕС и технологическим достижениям. Оба региона столкнулись с проблемами инфраструктуры, нормативных реформ и международного сотрудничества. Эти вопросы рассматриваются через примеры, данные и политические рамки.

Ключевые слова: Возобновляемые источники энергии, Солнечная энергия, Ветроэнергетика, Зеленый водород, Энергетический переход, Энергетическая безопасность, Устойчивое развитие

GEOPOLITICAL AND ECONOMIC ASPECTS OF THE MIDDLE CORRIDOR IN ADVANCING INTEGRATION AMONG TURKIC STATES

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Summary: *The Middle Corridor, or Trans-Caspian International Transport Route, has gained strategic importance amid rising geopolitical tensions and shifting global alignments. Positioned as a secure East-West link bypassing Russia and Iran, it fosters Turkic integration by enhancing political, economic, and logistical cooperation among member states. Backed by infrastructure investment and multilateral frameworks, the Corridor strengthens regional autonomy and reshapes Eurasian dynamics through alternative trade and transport routes.*

Key words: *Middle Corridor, Turkic states, regional integration, Eurasia, geopolitical transformation*

Introduction

As geopolitical processes develop unprecedentedly in the world, including on the Eurasian continent, worldwide trends are pushing countries to enhance their political, economic, technological capabilities and international transport corridors play far from negligible role. Against the backdrop of intensifying conflicts in key parts of the world (such as Eastern Europe and the Middle East) where traditional corridors run, great powers try to initiate new roots, which are more secure and effective. The idea for realizing the Middle Corridor, also known as the Trans-Caspian International Transport Route began to gain momentum namely with the increasing geopolitical tensions among powerful actors of the international system [8]. Indeed, playing the role of bridge between East and West, particularly China and Europe and passing through Central Asia and the Caucasus, the Middle Corridor became an additional catalyst for the revival of integration among Turkic states.

Geopolitical aspects of the Middle Corridor

The formation of the Turkic integration core in the Eurasian geopolitical space represents a strategic consolidation of political, economic, and cultural ties among Turkic states, aimed at enhancing regional cooperation and asserting greater autonomy within the international system. The Turkic states, situated along this corridor, are leveraging their geographic and cultural proximity to transform the region into a cohesive economic and logistical unit. This not only enhances their strategic significance but also fosters a more balanced multipolar order in Eurasia, which became even more visible in light of particular political events. Within this paradigm, Turkic world can perform as a bridge between East and West, insulated from major geopolitical fault lines. Taking into account the fact that the Middle Corridor was intended as a bypassing Russia and Iran, one should keep in mind interrelation of interests among Russia, Iran and China, especially under the latest conditions of geopolitical turbulence leading to the East-West division. At present, Russia enjoys close cooperation with China both in bilateral and multilateral basis. Being members of Shanghai